

PROBABILISTIC ASPECTS OF DAMAGE MODELLING IN CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING A FULLY AUTOMATED FINITE ELEMENT METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The analysis and prediction of the development of damage in composite materials represents a most important area of study at the present time. The application of the techniques of progressive damage modelling, using finite element analysis, has demonstrable value as a future design and assessment tool for routine use by materials engineers [1-3].

If these methodologies are to have value as a routine analytical tool, it is necessary to introduce automated functionality. The present work, using ABAQUS/Standard and /Explicit illustrates the development and use of a fully automated modelling methodology to study the effect of manufacturing defects and materials variability on damage development.

INTRODUCTION

The present work is divided up into two parts, both of which involve progressive damage modelling techniques. The first part applies ABAQUS/Standard and a simple, manually based modelling methodology, to study the effect of randomly distributed voids on the development of transverse ply cracking (tpc) damage in a cross-ply coupon specimen, loaded in tension. This introduces the concept of including manufacturing defects in the modelling of composite material behaviour and can be considered to be the first step in introducing probabilistic considerations into progressive damage modelling.

The second part applies a fully automated methodology based on ABAQUS/Explicit to the study of the effect of materials variability on damage development using the geometry of a typical aerospace component - a top-hat section stringer bonded to a skin and loaded in bending.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS USING ABAQUS

To provide an accurate model of the development of sub-critical damage in composite materials up to final failure, the following analysis strategy has been used:

- i. Construction of an ABAQUS [4] finite element mesh to represent the specimen or component, including the directionality of the mechanical properties of each ply and the detail of any defects present.
- ii. Application of small strain increments (typically 0.1%), with the stresses in each element being calculated after each increment.
- iii. For each element, comparison of the stress or strain system with criteria which indicate whether the element has suffered local damage.
- iv. For those elements which have suffered damage, degradation of their mechanical properties according to the type of damage that has occurred.
- v. Application of a further strain increment and then repetition of the steps above.
- vi. Identification of failure as the point at which the damage in the composite is such that it cannot support the applied load.

METHODOLOGY DEVELOPMENT

Development work has used both ABAQUS/Standard and ABAQUS/Explicit. The latter is conventionally used as a dynamic code, but it has been used here at static deformation rates. Its principal attractions are that it avoids the potential convergence problems that can occur with ABAQUS/Standard when element properties are degraded locally. Within ABAQUS/Explicit, fully-automated analysis is achieved via a suitably structured VUMAT sub-routine which controls the interrogation of the stresses and the degradation of properties. It is also structured so that graphical representations can be produced of the initiation and growth of different damage types, as well as predictions of the failure load.

DAMAGE CRITERIA

In the bulk of the modelling performed to date, local damage is represented by modifying the elastic moduli of appropriate elements in the mesh. Damaged elements are detected using a generalized stress-based criterion. When that is exceeded, the element is considered to have failed. Refinements needed here are that different criteria are needed for each damage type (the different damage types are controlled by different stress components), and that each damage type needs the degradation of a different combination of moduli.

Although there are several failure criteria available which can be used with CFRP, they are generally aimed at predicting the global failure of laminates which do not contain a stress-raiser such as a notch or crack. The need here was for an empirical generalized stress criterion which could be applied locally, and which was comprehensive enough to cover all damage mechanisms likely to occur under tensile loading. The criterion selected was a modified form of the Hill criterion; this has been reviewed and judged applicable to the analysis of CFRP [5]:

$$I_f = \frac{(\sigma_{11}/ult_{11})^2 + (\sigma_{22}/ult_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{33}/ult_{33})^2 + (\sigma_{12}/ult_{12})^2 + (\sigma_{13}/ult_{13})^2 + (\sigma_{23}/ult_{23})^2}{1} \quad (1)$$

and at failure, $I_f \geq 1$.

The "ult" factors in each term refer to the appropriate ultimate strengths which were defined as far as possible using published failure data.

The different types of failure that have been modelled using this criterion are shown schematically in Figure 1. To allow identification of when each type of damage occurs, the criterion shown in Equation (1) has been sub-divided by modifying it so that only the stress

components applicable to each type of damage are included viz.

- (a) Fibre failure (case (ii) in Figure 1)

$$I_f = (\sigma_{11}/ult_{11})^2 + (\sigma_{12}/ult_{12})^2 + (\sigma_{13}/ult_{13})^2 \quad (2)$$

- (b) Matrix failure (case (iii) in Figure 1)

$$I_f = (\sigma_{33}/ult_{33})^2 + (\sigma_{13}/ult_{13})^2 + (\sigma_{23}/ult_{23})^2 \quad (3)$$

This refers to a delamination-type failure within a single ply. It is important to note that it does not refer to conventional (ie. inter-ply) delamination and has been found to be of little significance in the test cases run to date. It is included for completeness.

- (c) Matrix splitting (case (iv) in Figure 1)

$$I_f = (\sigma_{22}/ult_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{12}/ult_{12})^2 + (\sigma_{23}/ult_{23})^2 \quad (4)$$

This covers both axial ply splitting and transverse ply cracking (tpc).

The sub-dividing of the criterion in this way allows the ABAQUS/Explicit VUMAT to define state-dependent variables (SDVs) which are used to flag-up when an element has suffered a certain type of damage. They can be called-up during post-processing to produce sequences of maps showing the development of damage, and are used to indicate which elements need to be assigned to sets with elastic properties degraded to simulate the appropriate type of damage. The modifications made to the sets of elastic properties for each type of damage are discussed below. Further to the discussion in (b) above, to represent inter-ply delamination it has proved necessary to move to 3D FE models which incorporate thin resin-rich layers between the plies.

MATERIAL PROPERTY DEGRADATION

The degradation rules used for each damage type are summarized in Figure 1, but are listed below in a more complete form. The directions are as shown in Figure 1 and the symbols used have their conventional meanings.

- (a) Fibre failure (case (ii) in Figure 1)

$$E_{11} = G_{12} = 0 \quad \& \quad \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0 \text{ for compatibility}$$

- (b) Matrix failure (case (iii) in Figure 1)

$$E_{33} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 0 \quad \& \quad \nu_{31} = \nu_{32} = 0 \text{ for compatibility}$$

- (c) Matrix splitting (case (iv) in Figure 1)

$$E_{22} = G_{12} = 0 \quad \& \quad \nu_{21} = \nu_{23} = 0 \text{ for compatibility}$$

Because this can represent, for example, axial splitting in the 0° ply or tpc (in the 90° ply) care is needed in the definition of the principal directions.

PREDICTION OF INTERLAMINAR DELAMINATION

As discussed, the damage types considered above do not include conventional interlaminar delamination. An attractive and practical approach to this is the introduction of additional thin layers between each ply to represent the resin-rich layers (RRLs) seen in practice between plies. These layers were assumed to have the moduli and failure strengths of the cured resin system i.e. with no fibre reinforcement. In-plane failure of these layers represents interlaminar delamination, and was determined by use of the same type of failure criterion as in Equation (1), modified to be consistent with in-plane failure.

PROBABILISTIC ASPECTS OF DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

The first part of the investigation used the ABAQUS/Standard, manual methodology to examine the effect of void distribution on the development of damage in an unnotched cross-ply tensile coupon. This can be considered to provide a representation of the effects of, for example, manufacturing defects on material behaviour. The approach used is similar to that reported during an earlier phase of the present work [6], when a two dimensional finite element model of a cross section of a four ply composite material with resin-rich layers was constructed.

In this case the model was randomly populated with voided areas using a volume fraction value as typically found in real materials. The progressive damage methodology was then applied and the evolution of damage was modelled under increasing load on the specimen.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The finite element model used in the present work is shown in Figure 2a, which is an axisymmetric model of one quarter of the section of the coupon. The model has four layers, the outer layer being a transverse (90°) layer separated from the longitudinal (0°) layer by a resin-rich layer; the central layer is a second resin-rich layer modelled at half thickness due to the symmetry of the layup. An increased degree of mesh refinement is used near the centre of the specimen, in particular in the transverse layer where transverse ply cracking is known to develop. This area is shown in more detail in Figure 2a. The material properties used for the various layers were those previously reported [6].

The area of increased refinement was then populated with voids. The distribution of void elements was generated randomly using a simple computer programme, to represent a void fraction of 2%, which is typical for such a material. The properties of degraded material were chosen to represent the voidage, i.e. the elements representing voids had zero stiffness in all directions. The resulting distribution of voids is shown in Figure 2b.

PREDICTED DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

The strain applied to the coupon was increased in increments of 0.1% and the modified Hill material failure criteria were applied. The development of damage i.e. transverse ply cracking, was monitored and is shown in Figures 2c and 2d at different strain levels.

Very little damage is seen to develop at small strain values (up to 0.5%), but there is clear evidence of the development of transverse ply cracking as the strain is increased further; six cracks appear at the surface at 0.7% strain. The crack density is thus 6 cracks / 10 mm (6 cracks/cm.) corresponding to an average inter-crack spacing of 1.67 mm.

The results may be compared with those reported by Takeda et al [7], who carried out investigations into the in-situ observation of failure processes in CFRP cross-ply laminates. In particular, Figure 3, which is reproduced from [7], shows the development of transverse ply cracking for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ_4/0^\circ)$ specimen as a function of applied strain. It is interesting to note that the onset of damage begins at between 0.5 and 1.0% strain and that the transverse crack density values are broadly consistent with those predicted by the present work.

In addition, it is interesting that Takeda et al used a probabilistic methodology (based on measured strength distributions for the material) to model the growth of damage and found that the predicted evolution of transverse ply crack damage was in better agreement with their experimental observations than predictions based on a deterministic approach. This effect is illustrated in Figure 3. It tends to confirm that the innate variability in the properties and microstructure of composite laminates renders a probabilistic approach most appropriate for the modelling of their mechanical behaviour.

REAL COMPONENT GEOMETRY

The work described here and previously [6,8] has only concerned the modelling of damage accumulation in simple tensile coupons. The intention of this work is to produce an analysis technique which can be applied to real component geometries and, eventually, complex loadings. The most recent work undertaken has been to set up a model of a top-hat section stringer bonded to a skin as this represents a widely-used aerospace design feature.

The axisymmetric mesh used for this analysis is shown in Figure 4 and is a cross-ply lay-up incorporating integral RRLs. Using the fully-automated analysis methodology in ABAQUS/Explicit, load/displacement and damage growth predictions have been made for the case of central deflections applied in the out-of-plane direction. Typical load/deflection predictions are shown in Figure 5, with representative delamination damage shown in Figure 6a, the delamination being represented as the shaded areas in the RRLs. Other damage mechanisms were also highlighted by this work.

PROBABILISTIC ASPECTS OF DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

In order to investigate the effects of material property variability on the behaviour of this component geometry, the material moduli and failure stresses were introduced as distributed quantities, using a distribution function taken from typical experimental results [9]. The variability was introduced simplistically by splitting the total distribution up into four segments, defining four types of material behaviour. The elements in the finite element model were then randomly allocated material properties while retaining the form of the property distribution. The predicted load/displacement curve is shown in Figure 5 and the corresponding delamination damage, shown in Figure 6b, is seen to be different to the undistributed material property case.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work has reached the following conclusions:

1. It has been demonstrated that an automated analysis methodology can be developed which allows the prediction of sub-critical damage accumulation in fibre-reinforced composites, through to final global failure.
2. Development of the model has proved possible because of the flexible user-definable

sub-routines which form part of the ABAQUS FE code. Most of the development work to date has concentrated on defining sub-routines which use stress-based damage criteria, and relatively simple rules for the degradation of the elastic moduli of damaged elements.

3. A probabilistic rather than a deterministic modelling methodology appears to be the most appropriate for application to composite materials because of their inherent variability.

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Figure 1. Damage Mechanisms

Figure 2. Cross-Ply Tensile Coupon - Section View

Figure 3. Transverse Crack Density Results from [7]

Figure 4. FE Model of Top-hat Stringer

Figure 5. Load/Displacement Curves for Stringer Model

(a) Original Material Properties

(b) Distributed Properties

Figure 6. Delamination Damage (Lighter Areas) in Resin-Rich Layers of Stringer